

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNET RESOURCES AND INTERNET APP IN DEVELOPING LEARNERS' WRITING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

In this globalized era, communication plays the most important role, and writing is not considered the most important. By writing we can express our professional communication. But not everyone has good writing skills. We know that in today's modern world is changing rapidly, which means that the Internet is becoming more and more important in every field. Now it requires new approaches to achieve new quality of education ensure a process of holistic personal development. The aim of this article is to improve learners' writing skills with the help of internet resources and application. It reveals the advantages of the internet in developing independent writing skill

Writing is the more difficult skill than other skills because of its complexity in spelling, pronunciation, vocabulary and grammatical structure. It has significant advantages because it allows one to:

- express one's personality;
- develop communication; and
- improve your capacity to analyze;
- make reasonable and convincing arguments
- allow a person to ponder on and re-evaluate his or her ideas afterwards;
- giving and receiving feedback
- prepare for school and work. [1, 1p.]

Writing is important because it is widely used in higher education and at work. Without writing skill learners will not be able to communicate well with professors, employers, colleagues, or anyone else. Most business

communications are in writing. Suggestions, notes, reports, applications, initial interviews, emails, etc. are part of the daily lives of college students and successful graduates. Writing occupies a unique position in language education. This is because learning writing involves three other language skills: listening, reading, and speaking practices and knowledge. In addition, coherence and cohesion which have to follow two important features of writing. One of the best ways to attract students to writing is to allow them to write as freely as possible early in the learning process and instill a sense of creativity in them. Creative writing is undeniably crucial in the development of writing abilities. [2, 56p]. for instance,

highlights the following advantages of creative writing:

- it supports language development at all levels: grammar, vocabulary, phonology, and discourse; it requires learners to manipulate language in fascinating and demanding ways in order to communicate distinctively individualized meanings;

- it requires a willingness to play with the language; and

It focuses more on the right side of the brain, with a focus on feelings, physical sensations, intuition, and musicality; it also provides opportunities for learners who are often left out of traditional learning procedures. Learners who engage in creative writing see a significant boost in self-confidence and self-esteem. Learners also have a tendency to discover new things about the language... and about themselves, fostering both personal and linguistic progress. Inevitably, these gains are accompanied with an increase in positive motivation. However, many students have difficulty writing creatively. he may not always be in front of a teacher who will check his mistakes. in such cases, internet resources and applications come to the rescue.[3]

According to recent study, integrating technology, such as the internet, improves and boosts students' general writing ability. "The internet represents a burgeoning literacy that engages readers of all ages and abilities," [4]

Our younger students are investigating the internet more and more, and there are more writing tools available on the internet. Internet resources have made an entire revolution in education, not only because they are convenient and accessible, but because they make the entire

process of teaching and learning more interesting and memorable. There are free and paid internet resources for students and they usually complement one another quite well. Each student will prefer different resources according to their subjects of interest and learning style, but there are universally great tools that impress nearly every student who tries them.

In order to help students locate the best online resources that will make their lives easier, we tailored a list of 15 most useful links that offer exactly what they need for achieving good grades.

1. The Rapid E-Learning Blog (Articulate Network)

The aim of this blog is to provide up-to-date information on different education-related topics that will help you become an e-learning pro.

2. Getting Smart

The website will help you to find resources that will increase your studying effectiveness.

3. Compass Learning Odyssey is a product that assesses the needs and strengths of a student and then prescribes a learning path according to his/her individual characteristics.

4. Saylor- this is the place where you can find free classes on all sorts of subjects.

5. Study Guide Zone- free resources to improve the scores on a standardized test. The website offers study exams for SAT, ACT, and GED among many other tests.

6. E-Learning Solutions Blog

This blog helps to find fresh information about the most popular and most useful e-learning tools.

7. Social Media Tools for College Students at Ninja Essays- Ninja Essays offers helpful educative social online

tools that will motivate you to learn new things each day by making the studying process easier and more fun.

- 8. E-Learning Center-** This comprehensive website will provide you with learning resources relevant to the subjects of Web Development and IT. Although some of the content is accessible only through paid subscription, there are also free resources that can be enough for you to advance your knowledge in these subjects.
- 9. Coursera-** Students can find free courses provided by prestigious universities. Almost all courses are offered, including humanities, computer science, business, mathematics, biology, and more.
- 10. Alison.** This website will provide you with all necessary tools for receiving free education of high quality. All you need is a will to learn new things
- 11. Knowledge Net** is the website you should visit whenever you need useful sources that will help you understand the lectures of IT-related subjects.
- 12. Homework-** Homework is convenient to quickly enter important tasks, course information, and homework assignments.
- 13. Course Buffet-** This search engine will lead you to open courseware accessible from different websites. This will save you from going from one source to another without finding what you need.
- 14. FindTutorials.com-** This website collects useful tutorials from across the web, so you will find literally anything you need there. The best thing about FindTutorials.com is that the users vote on the quality of all offered

tutorials, so you will know which links are worth clicking on.

- 15. Open Culture-** Open Culture delivers content from many different topics, from writing tips and literature characters to world history and wars.[5] One of the greatest benefits of the Internet technology is that now everyone has access to the information they need.

The advantages of using resource centre in training English

Internet resources are helpful for everyone who believes in lifelong learning and that knowledge must be freely shared. They are as following:

1. Paper Writings

Paper Writings is a website where students can turn for editing, proofreading, and academic assistance. From tips on writing essays to in-depth research, everything to do with writing and education will be done according to specifications and deadlines.

2. Ever note

This app is useful tools for organized life, for time management, for teamwork, for writing a book. Student can take recordings, snap photos, save links, handwriting, doodles, pieces of text, etc.

- 3. Dragon Dictation-** allow you to dictate rather than type, allowing you to work on your endless essays while on the go.

4. Go Conqr

With the help of platform learners can make study materials if they want they can share them with others or use ones from the vast library other users created. The most important side of the platform is learners can quiz yourself on the go while commuting or waiting in line at the supermarket, which is exactly what you expect from a flashcard format.

5. **Coursera** is a collection of free online courses developed in cooperation with leading universities. You will get a certificate for completing the course, so they will eventually get a degree, which is a good reward based on the knowledge gained.
6. **FastWeb** is an online service that connects students with the university that best suits their aspirations and abilities. FastWeb is very helpful. It allows you to search for and apply for various scholarships covering tuition fees.
7. **Open Culture**
It offers Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) that is, a free online lectures from renowned universities which provides with certificates, free materials – textbooks, audio books, literature works, language lessons, movies for cultural studies and many.
8. **Dictionary.com**–this app offers an online dictionary and thesaurus for students whose writing skills are not well developed.
9. **Grammarly**– you can easily check spelling and grammar mistakes checking in your writing.[7]
10. **Quetext**– this app is free online plagiarism detector and must-have app for everyone
11. **Teachers Pay Teachers** – this app helps especially teachers to buy course materials and essay prompts from other teachers.
12. **New York Times Writing Prompts** offers free writing prompts based on current events.
13. **Google Docs** - Google's free document editor. Works great with Google Classroom.
14. **Evernote**- Allows you to write on mobile, tablet, web, or desktop and keep your notebooks in sync.
15. **Notion** - Collaborate on writing, spreadsheets, and project management.
16. **TheGraide Network** - Feedback and scoring from remote, online teaching assistants.
17. **Peergrade** - A free online tool to facilitate student-to-student feedback sessions.
18. **Hemingway**- helps you refine your style and improve language, structure and lexicon
19. **Quill**- it offers various tools to help students with their writing including Quill Grammar Proofreader.
20. **OWL**- OWL, which belongs to Purdue University, has a huge online library that features a wide variety of materials covering different writing-related topics such as grammar and mechanics, professional writing, APA and MLA formatting guides, resume writing, research and citation tips, subject-specific writing and many more.
21. **Essay map**- this interactive graphic organizer helps students develop an outline that includes an introductory statement, main ideas they want to discuss or describe, supporting details, and a conclusion that summarizes the main ideas.[6]

To conclude, the Internet can be used to help students develop evaluative and critical skills, since one of the features of this new medium is that it provides a great variety of sources of information that

students need to evaluate for reliability, accuracy, authenticity and applicability.

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